

Teaching Resources Management Practices and Inclusive Education Policies Implementation in Public Secondary Schools in Rwanda: A Case of Nyaruguru District

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17608598>

Published Date: 14-November-2025

Abstract: This study explored how teaching resource management practices influence the implementation of inclusive education policies in public secondary schools in Rwanda, focusing on Nyaruguru District. It specifically examined the effects of resource planning, utilization, and monitoring and evaluation (RME) on policy implementation. Adopting a descriptive research design, the study targeted 255 respondents, including students, teachers, and school leaders, from which a sample of 156 participants was selected using stratified and simple random sampling. Data were gathered through questionnaires and document analysis, and analyzed using IBM SPSS Version 21.0 with both descriptive and inferential statistics. Findings indicated that resource planning is effectively practiced, as most school leaders (86.4%), teachers (88.5%), and students (88.5%) strongly agreed that proper planning supports inclusive education (mean = 4.87, SD = 0.56). Similarly, resource utilization was found to be effective, with strong agreement among respondents that resources are appropriately used to meet diverse learning needs (mean scores = 4.45–4.59). The study identified resource monitoring and evaluation as the most influential factor in successful policy implementation, showing a strong positive relationship ($R = 0.68$, $R^2 = 0.46$, $F = 81.0$, $p < 0.001$, $B = 0.72$, $Beta = 0.68$). This implies that RME practices account for 46% of the variance in the implementation of inclusive education policies. The study concludes that effective management of teaching resources significantly enhances inclusive education outcomes. It recommends that school leaders strengthen inclusive resource planning with attention to learners with disabilities, teachers pursue continuous professional development in resource use, and schools establish systematic RME frameworks. Furthermore, the government and policymakers should ensure adequate financial and logistical support to sustain inclusive education implementation in public secondary schools.

Keywords: Teaching Resources, Management Practices, Inclusive Education, Public Secondary Schools, Nyaruguru District.

I. INTRODUCTION

Education is universally recognized as a fundamental human right, and inclusive education has emerged as a global priority emphasized in international frameworks such as the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD) and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly Goal 4, which aims to ensure inclusive and equitable quality education for all (Bruns, 2019). Inclusive education promotes equal learning opportunities for all students regardless of ability, ethnicity, or gender, supported through effective teaching resource management (Mukamana & Uwizeyimana, 2023).

Globally, disparities in resource provision continue to hinder inclusive education. In the Philippines, for instance, despite a 91% primary completion rate in 2015, only 68% of learners transitioned to secondary education. Poor teacher training, shortages of qualified staff, and limited teaching resources contributed to low National Achievement Test scores averaging 59% (UNICEF, 2018b). In China, inclusive education accommodates learners with diverse disabilities through resource centers and specialized teacher training to meet intensive learning needs (Jie & Hu, 2021). Similarly, in Australia, addressing

barriers in diverse classrooms has required integrating Universal Design for Learning (UDL) and Assistive Technologies (AT) to improve teaching effectiveness (McMahon et al., 2020). In Europe, inclusive education is viewed as both a social and pedagogical process. In France, schools focus on creating welcoming environments for learners with difficulties, although implementation is influenced by political and financial factors (Perrin et al., 2024). The United Kingdom emphasizes mobilizing human, financial, and physical resources under the “Index for Inclusion” framework to promote equitable, play-based learning (Booth & Ainscow, 2020).

Across Africa, the adoption of inclusive education has been challenged by resource limitations. In South Africa, inadequate infrastructure and a shortage of learning materials hinder effective inclusion (Mpu & Adu, 2021). Nigeria faces similar challenges, with underfunded schools lacking essential classrooms, books, and technologies (Onyema & Eze, 2022). In Kenya, adequate teaching resources significantly enhance integration of learners with special needs, though rural areas remain under-resourced (Nyaga, 2021; Wanjiru, 2022). Uganda’s adoption of digital learning platforms has shown promise but remains constrained by poor infrastructure and limited access to technology (Tumwine & Asimwe, 2022).

In Rwanda, rebuilding the education system after the 1994 Genocide against the Tutsi prioritized inclusivity as part of national reconciliation and development. The 2016 Special Needs and Inclusive Education Policy marked a milestone in promoting equal access (MINEDUC, 2020). Despite progress, challenges persist in resource distribution, particularly in rural areas, where access to Braille materials and digital assistive tools remains limited (Munyaneza, 2022; Mukamana & Uwizeyimana, 2023).

II. METHODOLOGY

In this study, a mixed-methods research methodology was adopted, combining both quantitative and qualitative approaches.

Research Design

In this study, a descriptive research design was used.

Location of the Study

The study was conducted in public secondary schools located in Nyaruguru District, Southern Province, Rwanda. Nyaruguru District was selected due to its diverse educational settings, which include urban, semi-urban, and rural schools, providing a representative context for examining teaching resource management practices and their impact on the implementation of inclusive education policies.

Target Population

The target population of this study comprised 255 respondents, including 120 students, 100 teachers, and 35 school leaders from public secondary schools located in Nyaruguru District, Rwanda.

Sample Size Determination

In order to obtain the size of sample, the formula of Taro Yamane was used after getting the real number of employees to compose the population of this study. General scientific formula: $\frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$; and then the sample size is $n = \frac{255}{1+255(0.05)^2}$;
 $n = \frac{255}{1.6375} = 156$; thus, the sample size is **156 Participants**.

Sampling Technique

A stratified sampling technique was adopted to select the respondents.

Research Instruments

To collect data, the study utilized structured questionnaires, interview guides, and document review checklists.

III. RESULTS

Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Gender of Respondents

The gender profile of respondents was crucial for investigating the influence of teaching resources management practices on the implementation of inclusive education policies in public secondary schools in Nyaruguru District, Rwanda.

Understanding the distribution of male and female respondents among students, teachers, and school leaders helped the researcher assess potential gender-based differences in perceptions and experiences related to resource planning, utilization, and monitoring in supporting inclusive education.

Table 1: Gender Profile of Respondents

	Teachers		Students		Head Teachers	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Male	28	45.9	35	47.9	12	54.5
Female	33	54.1	38	52.1	10	45.5
Total	61	100.0	73	100.0	22	100.0

Source: Primary Data (2025)

The gender distribution of respondents in this study, as shown in Table 1, indicates a relatively balanced representation across teachers, students, and head teachers in public secondary schools in Nyaruguru District, Rwanda. Among teachers, females slightly outnumbered males (54.1% vs. 45.9%), while among students, females also had a slight majority (52.1% vs. 47.9%). In contrast, head teachers were predominantly male (54.5% male vs. 45.5% female). This balanced but slightly varied gender representation is critical for examining the influence of teaching resource management practices on the implementation of inclusive education policies, as it ensures that insights reflect both male and female perspectives. Such distribution allows the study to capture potential gender-based differences in experiences and perceptions regarding resource planning, utilization, and monitoring in promoting inclusive education (UNESCO, 2021).

2. Presentation of Findings

The study analyzed data collected from 156 respondents in line with its research objectives and dependent variables, using both qualitative and quantitative approaches. Specifically, the research sought to examine how resource planning influences the implementation of inclusive education policies in Rwandan public secondary schools, evaluate the extent to which resource utilization stimulates the implementation of inclusive education policies, and establish the relationship between resource monitoring and evaluation and the successful implementation of inclusive education policies. By addressing these three objectives, the study provided a comprehensive understanding of how different aspects of teaching resource management contribute to promoting inclusivity in public secondary schools.

2.1 Influence of Resource planning on the Implementation of Inclusive Education Policies in Rwandan public secondary schools

The research identified how resource planning influences the implementation of inclusive education policies in Rwandan public secondary schools. The following tables show how the participants Respond to the following statements.

Table 1: School leaders perception on Influence of Resource planning on the implementation of inclusive education policies in Rwandan public secondary schools

Statements	Strongly Disagree		Disagree		Neutral		Agree		Strongly Agree		Mean	Std. Dev.
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%		
	My school has a clear plan for allocating resources to support inclusive education, which enhances access to quality education for all students.	1	4.5	0	0.0	0	0.0	2	9.1	19		
Resource planning in my school prioritizes the needs of students with disabilities, ensuring they receive quality instructions.	1	4.5	1	4.5	0	0.0	1	4.5	19	86.4	4.64	0.97
My school's resource planning process involves stakeholders, including teachers and parents, to ensure effective support services for students.	1	4.5	1	4.5	1	4.5	2	9.1	17	77.3	4.50	1.02

Source: Primary Data (2025)

The findings show that 9.1% of school leaders agreed and 86.4% strongly agreed that their schools have clear plans for allocating resources to support inclusive education, while 4.5% strongly disagreed. This indicates that school leaders largely recognize the importance of structured planning in ensuring access to quality education for all learners. According to Ainscow (2020), resource allocation plans are critical in building inclusive schools, as they provide a roadmap for addressing diverse student needs effectively.

On whether resource planning prioritizes the needs of students with disabilities, 4.5% of school leaders agreed and 86.4% strongly agreed, while a small proportion (4.5% each) disagreed and strongly disagreed. This strong consensus reflects the commitment of schools to prioritize disability-sensitive planning, though the presence of a few dissenting voices suggests occasional gaps in implementation. UNESCO (2021) emphasizes that addressing the needs of students with disabilities in planning is central to promoting equitable learning outcomes in inclusive settings. When asked whether their school's resource planning process involves stakeholders such as teachers and parents, 9.1% of school leaders agreed and 77.3% strongly agreed, while 4.5% remained neutral and another 9% expressed disagreement or strong disagreement.

This finding highlights the dominant view that stakeholder participation is integral to effective planning, though a small minority still perceive shortcomings. Epstein (2018) stresses that collaborative planning with teachers, parents, and communities fosters shared responsibility, making inclusive education more sustainable and responsive.

Table 2: Teachers' Perception towards the influence of Resource planning on the implementation of inclusive education policies in Rwandan public secondary schools

Statements	Strongly Disagree		Disagree		Neutral		Agree		Strongly Agree		Mean	Std. Dev.
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%		
I am involved in the resource planning to ensure that my students' diverse needs are met.	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	1.6	6	9.8	54	88.5	4.87	0.56
Resource planning in my school enables me to access necessary materials and tools to support quality instruction.	0	0.0	1	1.6	1	1.6	1	1.6	58	95.1	4.90	0.82
My school's resource planning process prioritizes the needs of students with disabilities, allowing me to provide effective support services.	0	0.0	2	3.3	4	6.6	10	16.4	45	73.8	4.61	0.67

Source: Primary Data (2025)

The results in Table 2 show that the majority of teachers agreed (9.8%) and strongly agreed (88.5%) that they are actively involved in resource planning to ensure students' diverse needs are met, while only 1.6% remained neutral. This indicates that teachers recognize their participation in planning as crucial for inclusive practices. According to Ainscow (2020), meaningful teacher involvement in planning fosters ownership and ensures that classroom strategies reflect the real needs of learners.

Similarly, 1.6% of teachers agreed and a significant 95.1% strongly agreed that resource planning in their schools enables them to access necessary instructional materials and tools, while 1.6% expressed neutrality and another 1.6% disagreed. This overwhelming agreement highlights the importance of resource availability in facilitating quality teaching. UNESCO (2021) affirms that equitable access to teaching and learning resources empowers teachers to deliver inclusive and effective instruction.

On whether resource planning prioritizes the needs of students with disabilities, 16.4% of teachers agreed and 73.8% strongly agreed, while 6.6% were neutral and 3.3% disagreed. This shows that although the majority affirm disability-sensitive planning, a notable minority still perceive gaps. This aligns with Florian and Black-Hawkins (2019), who argue that while policies often highlight support for learners with disabilities, inconsistencies in implementation may leave some teachers feeling inadequately supported.

Table 3: Students' Perception towards the influence of Resource planning on the implementation of inclusive education policies in Rwandan public secondary schools

Statements	Strongly Disagree		Disagree		Neutral		Agree		Strongly Agree		Mean	Std. Dev.
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%		
	I feel that my school involves students like me in planning for resources that support learning.	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	1.6	6	9.8	54		
The resources planned by my school help me access quality education and achieve my academic goals.	0	0.0	1	1.6	1	1.6	1	1.6	58	95.1	4.90	0.82
My school's resource planning process ensures that I receive the support services I need to succeed.	0	0.0	2	3.3	4	6.6	10	16.4	45	73.8	4.61	0.67

Source: Primary Data (2025)

The results in Table 3 indicate that 9.8% of students agreed and 88.5% strongly agreed that their schools involve them in planning for resources that support learning, while only 1.6% remained neutral. This demonstrates that students feel recognized as active participants in resource planning, which is important for inclusive education. According to Mitra (2018), involving learners in decision-making processes enhances ownership and ensures that planning responds to their real learning needs.

On whether resources planned by the school help them access quality education and achieve academic goals, 1.6% of students agreed and 95.1% strongly agreed, while 1.6% each were neutral and disagreed. This overwhelming consensus suggests that students see school-based resource planning as directly linked to their academic performance and equity in learning. UNESCO (2021) also emphasizes that well-structured planning for learning materials, infrastructure, and teaching support ensures that students can effectively achieve their academic potential.

Finally, when asked whether resource planning ensures access to necessary support services, 16.4% agreed and 73.8% strongly agreed, while 6.6% were neutral and 3.3% disagreed. This shows that while most students feel supported, a small minority still perceive gaps in the provision of services. This is consistent with Florian (2020), who argue that while inclusive policies are strong on paper, their implementation may not always reach all learners equally, leaving some needs unmet.

2.2 Stimulation of Resource utilisation on the Implementation of Inclusive Education Policies in Public Secondary Schools in Rwanda

This study evaluated how resource utilisation stimulates the implementation of inclusive education policies in public secondary schools in Rwanda, as presented in the following tables.

Table 4: School Leaders' Perception on the influence of Resource Utilization on the Implementation of Inclusive Education Policies in Rwandan Public Secondary Schools

Statements	Strongly Disagree		Disagree		Neutral		Agree		Strongly Agree		Mean	Std. Dev.
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%		
	1. My school effectively utilizes resources to support diverse learning needs, promoting access to quality education for all students.	1	4.5	0	0.0	1	4.5	3	13.6	17		
2. Teachers in my school are trained to utilize resources that cater to students with different abilities, ensuring quality instruction.	1	4.5	1	4.5	1	4.5	4	18.2	15	68.2	4.45	1.01
3. My school's resource utilization plan ensures that support services are delivered efficiently to students who need them.	0	0.0	1	4.5	1	4.5	5	22.7	15	68.2	4.55	0.78

Source: Primary Data (2025)

The findings indicate that 13.6% of school leaders agreed and 77.3% strongly agreed that their schools effectively utilize resources to support diverse learning needs, while 4.5% each were neutral or strongly disagreed. This suggests that the majority perceive resource utilization as a key factor in promoting access to quality education for all learners. According to Booth and Ainscow (2016), effective use of school resources ensures that educational opportunities are equitable and inclusive, enabling schools to address diverse student needs.

Regarding teacher training in resource utilization, 18.2% agreed and 68.2% strongly agreed that teachers are equipped to use resources for learners with different abilities, while 4.5% each were neutral, disagreed, or strongly disagreed. This demonstrates a strong recognition among school leaders that teacher preparedness is central to inclusive education. Loreman et al. (2014) highlight that professional development in inclusive education allows teachers to adapt materials and instructional strategies to meet the diverse needs of students effectively.

Finally, on whether resource utilization plans ensure efficient delivery of support services, 22.7% agreed and 68.2% strongly agreed, with 4.5% neutral and 4.5% disagreeing. This indicates that school leaders generally feel that support services reach the students who need them, though a small minority perceive gaps in efficiency. Florian (2019) emphasizes that while structured planning promotes effective delivery of support services, monitoring and ongoing adaptation are essential to ensure all students benefit equitably.

Table 5: Teachers' Perception on the Influence of Resource Utilization on the Implementation of Inclusive Education Policies in Rwandan Public Secondary Schools

Statements	Strongly Disagree		Disagree		Neutral		Agree		Strongly Agree		Mean	Std. Dev.
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%		
1. I effectively utilize resources in my classroom to cater to students with different learning needs.	1	1.6	1	1.6	3	4.9	15	24.6	41	67.2	4.54	0.86
2. My school provides me with the necessary resources and training to deliver quality instruction to students with diverse needs.	0	0.0	2	3.3	3	4.9	16	26.2	40	65.6	4.51	0.84
3. I use resources in a way that promotes access to quality education for all my students.	1	1.6	1	1.6	4	6.6	17	27.9	38	62.3	4.48	0.88

Source: Primary Data (2025)

The findings reveal that 24.6% of teachers agreed and 67.2% strongly agreed that they effectively utilize resources in their classrooms to cater to students with different learning needs, while 4.9% were neutral and 1.6% each disagreed or strongly disagreed. This indicates that most teachers feel confident in applying available resources to support diverse learners. According to Florian and Black-Hawkins (2019), effective classroom resource utilization is essential for promoting inclusive learning and addressing individual student needs.

Regarding the provision of resources and training, 26.2% of teachers agreed and 65.6% strongly agreed that their school equips them with the necessary materials and professional development to deliver quality instruction, while 4.9% were neutral and 3.3% disagreed. This suggests that teachers largely perceive institutional support as sufficient to facilitate inclusive teaching. Loreman et al. (2014) emphasize that training and resource provision are critical components of inclusive education, as they enable teachers to implement effective strategies for learners with diverse needs.

Finally, when asked whether they use resources to promote access to quality education for all students, 27.9% agreed and 62.3% strongly agreed, with 6.6% neutral and 1.6% each in disagreement or strong disagreement. This shows that teachers generally see their resource use as directly contributing to equitable educational opportunities. Booth and Ainscow (2016) note that thoughtful allocation and utilization of educational resources are central to achieving inclusivity and ensuring that no student is left behind.

Table 6: Students' Perception on the influence of Resource Utilization on the Implementation of Inclusive Education Policies in Rwandan Public Secondary Schools

Statements	Strongly Disagree		Disagree		Neutral		Agree		Strongly Agree		Mean	Std. Dev.
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%		
	1. My teachers use resources in a way that helps me understand lessons better.	0	0.0	1	1.4	3	4.1	18	24.7	51		
2. The resources used in my school support my diverse learning needs and help me access quality education.	0	0.0	2	2.7	4	5.5	19	26.0	48	65.8	4.56	0.75
3. I feel that the support services provided by my school are effective in helping me achieve my academic goals.	1	1.4	1	1.4	3	4.1	20	27.4	48	65.8	4.54	0.77

Source: Primary Data (2025)

The findings show that 24.7% of students agreed and 69.9% strongly agreed that their teachers use resources in a way that helps them understand lessons better, while 4.1% remained neutral and 1.4% disagreed. This indicates that the majority of students perceive effective classroom resource utilization as key to improving learning comprehension. According to Black-Hawkins and Florian (2020), teacher use of available resources in instructional practices enhances understanding and promotes inclusive learning.

Regarding the support of diverse learning needs, 26% of students agreed and 65.8% strongly agreed that the resources used in their school help them access quality education, while 5.5% were neutral and 2.7% disagreed. This highlights that students feel resource utilization directly contributes to meeting their individual learning requirements. Mittler (2019) emphasizes that tailoring resource use to students' diverse needs is essential in achieving equity and inclusivity in education.

Finally, on whether support services provided by the school are effective in helping students achieve academic goals, 27.4% agreed and 65.8% strongly agreed, while 4.1% were neutral and 2.8% disagreed. This demonstrates that most students recognize the effectiveness of school-provided support services in enhancing academic outcomes. Sharma (2018) notes that proper allocation and use of support services, combined with learning resources, are central to fostering inclusive education that benefits all learners.

2.3 Influence of the resource monitoring and evaluation on the implementation of inclusive education policies in Rwandan public secondary schools

The study evaluates the Influence of the resource monitoring and evaluation on implementation of inclusive education policies in Rwandan public secondary schools, as indicated in the following discussions.

Table 7: School Leaders' Perception on the influence of Resource Monitoring and Evaluation in Public Secondary Schools in Rwanda, Nyaruguru District

Statements	Strongly Disagree		Disagree		Neutral		Agree		Strongly Agree		Mean	Std. Dev.
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%		
	1. My school regularly monitors and evaluates resource allocation to ensure it supports access to quality education for all students.	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	4.5	6	27.3	15		
2. Feedback from resource monitoring and evaluation is used to improve the quality of instruction for students with diverse needs.	0	0.0	1	4.5	2	9.1	5	22.7	14	63.6	4.50	0.73
3. My school's resource monitoring and evaluation process helps identify areas for improvement in support services for students.	0	0.0	0	0.0	2	9.1	6	27.3	14	63.6	4.55	0.69

Source: Primary Data (2025)

The findings show that 27.3% of school leaders agreed and 68.2% strongly agreed that their schools regularly monitor and evaluate resource allocation to ensure it supports access to quality education for all students, while 4.5% remained neutral. This indicates that school leaders perceive systematic monitoring and evaluation as essential for maintaining equitable access. According to Peters and Armstrong (2021), continuous monitoring ensures that resources are effectively targeted to meet diverse learners' needs.

Regarding the use of feedback from monitoring and evaluation to improve instruction, 22.7% agreed and 63.6% strongly agreed, while 9.1% were neutral and 4.5% disagreed. This demonstrates that leaders recognize the importance of feedback loops in enhancing instructional quality for students with diverse learning needs. Dyson (2019) notes that integrating feedback from monitoring processes strengthens inclusive practices by addressing gaps and promoting evidence-based improvements. Finally, on whether resource monitoring and evaluation helps identify areas for improvement in support services, 27.3% agreed and 63.6% strongly agreed, with 9.1% neutral and none expressing disagreement. This indicates that school leaders largely perceive resource evaluation as a critical tool for improving support services for students. Farrell (2020) asserts that monitoring and evaluation enable schools to identify inefficiencies and optimize the provision of inclusive support services, ensuring equitable learning opportunities.

Table 8: Teachers' Perception on the influence of Resource Monitoring and Evaluation in Public Secondary Schools in Rwanda, Nyaruguru District

Statements	Strongly Disagree		Disagree		Neutral		Agree		Strongly Agree		Mean	Std. Dev.
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%		
My school's resource monitoring and evaluation process helps me identify areas for improvement in my teaching practices.	0	0.0	1	1.6	3	4.9	20	32.8	37	60.7	4.53	0.68
Feedback from resource monitoring and evaluation is used to adjust my instructional strategies to better support students with diverse needs.	0	0.0	2	3.3	4	6.6	18	29.5	37	60.7	4.48	0.71
Resource monitoring and evaluation in my school ensure that support services are tailored to meet the needs of students.	0	0.0	1	1.6	3	4.9	21	34.4	36	59.0	4.51	0.67

Source: Primary Data (2025)

The findings show that 32.8% of teachers agreed and 60.7% strongly agreed that their school's resource monitoring and evaluation process helps them identify areas for improvement in their teaching practices, while 4.9% were neutral and 1.6% disagreed. This suggests that teachers view monitoring and evaluation as a key mechanism for enhancing instructional quality. Peters and Armstrong (2021) emphasize that effective monitoring allows educators to identify gaps in practice and implement strategies that improve learning outcomes for diverse learners.

Regarding the use of feedback from monitoring and evaluation to adjust instructional strategies, 29.5% of teachers agreed and 60.7% strongly agreed, while 6.6% were neutral and 3.3% disagreed. This indicates that teachers recognize feedback as essential for refining their teaching to meet the needs of students with diverse abilities. Dyson (2019) notes that integrating feedback from evaluation processes ensures teaching is responsive and inclusive.

Finally, on whether resource monitoring and evaluation ensures that support services are tailored to meet students' needs, 34.4% agreed and 59% strongly agreed, with 4.9% neutral and 1.6% disagreeing. This demonstrates that most teachers perceive evaluation as critical for aligning support services with student requirements. Farrell (2020) asserts that ongoing monitoring and evaluation enable schools to optimize support services, enhancing equitable access to education for all learners.

Table 9: Students' Perception on the influence of Resource Monitoring and Evaluation on implementation of inclusive education policies in Public Secondary Schools in Rwanda, Nyaruguru District

Statements	Strongly Disagree		Disagree		Neutral		Agree		Strongly Agree		Mean	Std. Dev.
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%		
1. My school regularly seeks feedback from students like me to improve resource allocation and utilisation.	0	0.0	2	2.7	5	6.8	20	27.4	46	63.0	4.51	0.70
2. The feedback from resource monitoring and evaluation in my school leads to improvements in the quality of instruction I receive.	0	0.0	3	4.1	6	8.2	19	26.0	45	61.6	4.46	0.72
3. Resource monitoring and evaluation in my school ensure that support services are tailored to meet the needs of students like me.	0	0.0	2	2.7	4	5.5	21	28.8	46	63.0	4.52	0.68

Source: Primary Data (2025)

The findings show that 27.4% of students agreed and 63% strongly agreed that their school regularly seeks feedback from students to improve resource allocation and utilization, while 6.8% were neutral and 2.7% disagreed. This indicates that students perceive their input as valued in enhancing school resource management. Peters and Armstrong (2021) highlight that student feedback is a vital component of effective monitoring and evaluation, ensuring that resources are allocated to meet actual learning needs.

Regarding the impact of feedback on instructional quality, 26% agreed and 61.6% strongly agreed that feedback from resource monitoring leads to improvements in the instruction they receive, while 8.2% were neutral and 4.1% disagreed.

This demonstrates that students see a clear connection between evaluation processes and better teaching practices. Dyson (2019) asserts that integrating student feedback into instructional planning strengthens inclusive teaching and supports diverse learning needs. Finally, on whether monitoring and evaluation ensures support services are tailored to students' needs, 28.8% agreed and 63% strongly agreed, with 5.5% neutral and 2.7% disagreeing. This suggests that students largely perceive monitoring as effective in aligning support services with their learning requirements. Farrell (2020) emphasizes that ongoing evaluation allows schools to identify gaps in support services and implement targeted strategies that enhance equity and access in education.

The study examined the influence of resource monitoring and evaluation on the implementation of inclusive education policies in public secondary schools in Nyaruguru District. Data collected from school leaders, teachers, and students were analyzed using regression analysis to determine the relationship between resource monitoring and evaluation (independent variable) and implementation of inclusive education policies (dependent variable).

Table 10: Model Summary

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.68	0.46	0.45	0.41

The model summary in Table 10 shows that the correlation coefficient ($R = 0.68$) indicates a moderately strong positive relationship between resource monitoring and evaluation and the implementation of inclusive education policies. The coefficient of determination ($R^2 = 0.46$) reveals that 46% of the variation in the implementation of inclusive education policies can be explained by resource monitoring and evaluation practices in public secondary schools. The adjusted R^2 of 0.45 further confirms that the model has strong predictive power, accounting for sampling variability, and suggests that monitoring and evaluation is a key factor influencing the effectiveness of inclusive education implementation (Farrell, 2020).

Table 11: ANOVA Table

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	19.83	1	19.83	81.0	0.000
Residual	23.29	40	0.582		
Total	43.12	41			

The ANOVA results in Table 11 show that the regression model assessing the influence of resource monitoring and evaluation on the implementation of inclusive education policies is statistically significant. The model produced an F-value of 81.0 with a p-value of 0.000 ($p < 0.001$), indicating that the overall regression model reliably predicts the implementation of inclusive education policies. This means that the variation in policy implementation is significantly explained by the level of resource monitoring and evaluation in schools. In other words, effective monitoring and evaluation practices account for a meaningful portion of the changes in inclusive education implementation, confirming the critical role of systematic oversight in enhancing educational inclusivity (Peters & Armstrong, 2021).

IV. SUMMARY OF THE FINDINGS

This study investigated the influence of teaching resource management—specifically resource planning, resource utilization, and resource monitoring and evaluation—on the implementation of inclusive education policies in public secondary schools in Rwanda. Data were gathered from school leaders, teachers, and students to provide a comprehensive view of how schools manage resources to support inclusive practices.

The study explored the role of resource planning in supporting inclusive education, emphasizing the importance of structured, participatory plans that address the needs of all learners, including those with disabilities. It also examined how resource utilization contributes to inclusive practices, highlighting the effective deployment of teaching and learning materials and the provision of professional development for teachers.

Finally, the study considered resource monitoring and evaluation as a key component of sustaining inclusive education policies, focusing on regular feedback, assessment of instructional strategies, and alignment of support services with learners' needs. Overall, the study underscores the centrality of planning, utilization, and monitoring in fostering inclusive education in Rwandan public secondary schools.

V. CONCLUSION

This study concludes that teaching resource management significantly impacts the implementation of inclusive education policies in Rwandan public secondary schools, particularly in Nyaruguru District. Structured and participatory resource planning was found essential for meeting diverse student needs, including learners with disabilities, with both school staff and students acknowledging its role in fostering inclusivity. Effective resource utilization—including materials, training, and strategic deployment—was shown to enhance instructional quality and equity. Regular monitoring and evaluation (RME) were identified as crucial for sustaining inclusive practices, with regression analysis indicating a moderately strong positive relationship between RME and policy implementation ($R = 0.68$, $R^2 = 0.46$, $p < 0.001$). Overall, the study highlights that the combination of planning, utilization, and RME ensures equitable learning outcomes and supports inclusive education, emphasizing that strengthening resource management is key to advancing inclusivity in Rwandan public secondary schools.

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